

Management's Role and Competence in HRD: An Evaluation

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Abstract

The human resources development process in many organizations begins with the hiring of a new employee and continues throughout that employee's employment with the company. HR development is intended to provide employees with the knowledge they need to adapt to the culture of the firm and perform their jobs efficiently. The management of an organization plays an important role in the formulation and implementation of human resource development programmes and policies. This largely depends on their willingness and competencies to introduce such programme in the organization. The present paper is an attempt to evaluate the role, willingness and competencies of management of Himachal Road Transport Corporation (HRTC) and Himachal Pradesh Tourism Development Corporation towards human resource development in their respective organization.

Keywords: HRD, Management, Management Willingness, Management Competency

1. Introduction

Human resources development (HRD) is a broad term that describes the wide range of training and development programmes offered by businesses to improve their employees' knowledge, skills, education, and talents. The human resources development process in many organizations begins with the hiring of a new employee and continues throughout that employee's employment with the company. Many personnel enter an organization with just rudimentary skills and experience, and they must be trained to perform their duties efficiently. Others may have the requisite abilities for the position but lack knowledge about the company. HR development is intended to provide employees with the knowledge they need to adapt to the culture of the firm and perform their jobs efficiently. (Scalia, 2016). HRD is the framework that helps the employees in developing their skills (both individual and organizational), knowledge, and abilities. It includes such opportunities as employees training, career development, performance appraisal and development etc. HRD is an organized learning activity arranged within an organization to

improve performance and personal growth to improve the job, the individual or the organization (McLagan, 1989).

HRD is a process, not merely a set of mechanisms and techniques. The mechanisms and techniques such as performance appraisal, counselling, training and organisation development interventions are used to initiate, facilitate, and continuously promote this process. Because the process has no limit, the mechanisms may need to be examined periodically to see whether they are promoting or hindering the process. Organisations can facilitate this process of development by planning for it, allocating organisational resources for the purpose, and by exemplifying an HRD philosophy that values human beings and promotes their development (Rudrabasavaraj, 1987). The management of an organization plays an important role in the formulation and implementation of human resource development programmes and policies. This largely depends on their willingness and competencies to introduce such programme in the organization. The present paper is an attempt to evaluate the role, willingness and competencies of management of Himachal Road Transport Corporation (HRTC) and Himachal Pradesh Tourism Development Corporation towards human resource development in their respective organization.

2. Review of literature

Billimoria (1997) in his article, "HRD Strategies for Globalization", emphasized the varied HRD strategies, some pertain to person in the work unit and others to external strategies. The study reveals that an HRD specialist must accept that the more a manager climbs up the executive ladder, the lesser he gets to hear the happenings to human resources in the line down below. Tiwari (2001) in his study reveals that the development of human resources for an area is influenced by socio-economic factors. Urbanization, working forces, literacy and particularly female literacy are the main factors of development. Tripathi and Tripathi (2002) in their study concluded that the combination of reward and participation, proficiency and responsibility factors play an important role to increase the level of job satisfaction. Saini (2005) has concluded that vocational training and better education as a media for human resource development are getting attention in the sphere of developing world-class manpower. Bhatia (2007) in a study found that leveraging the human potential for excellence is an integral part of organizational strategy and that strategy implementation entails performing practical management tasks aimed at making things happen. It was felt that a thorough evaluation of human resource function is imperative, both to rejuvenate it and to make it more business-driven. Jaiswal and Singh

(2014) found that there is a positive relationship between Organizational Effectiveness and Human Resource Development Climate.. Jacobs (2017) concluded that measuring the outcomes of knowledge-based tasks may be accomplished through considering measuring employee outcomes at different stages of task performance, including outcomes that occur at the beginning of the task, during the task, and at the conclusion of the task. Patel (2019) concluded that overall, the respondents are satisfied with the performance appraisal method. It also increases the effectiveness and productivity of employees and the organization as a whole.

3. Objective and Methodology

The present paper aims at evaluating the opinion of the employees of Himachal Road Transport Corporation and Himachal Pradesh Tourism Development Corporation towards management role, willingness and competency towards human resource development. To achieve the said objective, primary data have been collected. A sample of 80 lower-level employees (40 from each corporation) have been selected and their opinion have been collected through administering an interview schedule.

4. Tools and Techniques

Following tools and techniques have been used to analyze the collected data.

- (a) **Measurement of Central Tendency or Arithmetic Mean:** The arithmetic mean has been applied to study the opinion of the respondents on 5-point scale. The arithmetic mean has been calculated by assigning numerical values to the qualitative statements. These values have been assigned for these qualitative responses as '1' for Highly Incompetent, '2' for 'Incompetent', '3' for 'neutral', '4' for 'Competent' and '5' for 'Highly Competent'. It has been calculated by applying the following formula:

$$\text{Formula: } \bar{x} = \frac{\sum fx}{\sum f}$$

Here, \bar{x} = Arithmetic mean; f = Frequency distribution on 5-point scale. x = Variable values.

- (b) **Standard Deviation:** The standard deviation measures the absolute variability of distribution. Hence, standard deviation is extremely useful in judging the representativeness of the mean.

$$\text{Formula: } = \sqrt{\frac{\sum (x - \bar{x})^2}{N}}$$

= Standard Deviation; \bar{x} = Mean ; N = Total number of observations.

(c) Chi-square Test: The chi-square test as a test of goodness of fit has been used to analyze the magnitude of difference in the opinion of respondents between observed distribution and the expected distribution under the assumption that it is equally distributed on 2 or 3 or 5 -point scale. This test has been applied to study whether significant differences exist in the distribution of opinion of respondents or not.

$$\text{Formula: } \chi^2 = \sum \frac{(O - E)^2}{E}$$

Where, χ^2 = Chi-square; O = Observed frequencies; E = Expected frequencies

The calculated value of chi-square has been compared with the table value at the desired level of significance with the maximum cut-off point being 5 per cent. The difference in distribution of opinion on 2 or 3 or 5-point scale has been treated as significant if the calculated value of chi-square is greater than the relevant table value at 5 per cent level of significance.

5. Results and Discussions

The respondents' opinion has been taken on various aspects, such as management inclination, management's willingness, attitude and knowledge towards human resource development. The opinion has also been taken on the competency of management and their experience and expertise in HRD. The analysis of the collected data and results reached have been discussed under various headings as follows:

5.1. Opinion about Management's inclination

The opinion of lower-level employees about management's inclination towards the improvement of human resources in the organization has been collected and shown in

Table 1.

Table 1: Management's Inclination

Response	HRTC	HPTDC	Total
Yes	11(27.50)	15(37.50)	26(32.50)
No	15(37.50)	7(17.50)	22(27.50)
No opinion	14(35.00)	18(45.00)	32(40.00)
Total	40(100.00)	40(100.00)	80(100.00)
$\chi^2 = 4.024$; $\chi^2_{.05} = 5.991$; $p > .05$			

Note: χ^2 denotes Chi-square, $\chi^2_{.05}$ denotes Critical value or Tabular value of Chi-square.
ii) Figures in parenthesis represent percentage.

Source: Field survey.

Data in Table 1 depict that out of total respondents 32.50 per cent accepted the management's inclination towards administrative philosophy. Whereas 27.50 per cent of respondents didn't accept it. While 40.00 per cent of respondents didn't furnish their opinion on this question. The calculated value (4.024) of χ^2 test is lowest than the tabular value (5.991) at 5 per cent level of significance. It indicates that there is no significant difference in respondents' opinions. Hence, it can be said that in most of the cases the management didn't incline towards the administrative philosophy.

5.2. Opinion about Management's Willingness

The development and growth of an organization depend on its human resource. The human resource can give their best only if the human resource development is introduced in the organization. For this management's willingness is a pre-requisite. In this regard, the data have been collected from the lower-level employees and presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Management's Willingness to introduce HRD Programme

Response	HRTC	HPTDC	Total
Yes	12(30.00)	20(50.00)	32(40.00)
No	16(40.00)	11(27.50)	27(33.75)
No opinion	12(30.00)	9(22.50)	21(26.25)
Total	40(100.00)	40(100.00)	80(100.00)
$\chi^2 = 3.354$; $\chi^2_{.05} = 5.991$; $p > .05$			

Note: χ^2 denotes Chi-square, $\chi^2_{.05}$ denotes Critical value or Tabular value of Chi-square.
ii) Figures in parenthesis represent percentage.

Source: Field survey.

Data show that the majority of respondents (40.00 per cent) in HRTC reported that the management was not willing, while a majority of respondents (50.00 per cent) in HPTDC reported that management was willing to introduce the HRD programme. Overall, 40.00 per cent of respondents opined that management is willing, 33.75 per cent reported not being willing and 26.25 per cent of respondents restrained themselves from answering the question. The calculated value (3.354) of χ^2 test is lower than the tabular value (5.991) at a 5 per cent level of significance. It indicates that there is no significant difference in respondents' opinions. Hence, it can be said that though the majority of respondents accepted that management was willing to introduce the HRD programme in the organization, that was not enough because the percentage of those respondents who didn't accept it or were restrained to say anything cannot be ignored. It gives an impression that the management of both organizations is not willing to introduce the HRD programme.

5.3. Management Knowledge and Positive attitude

The knowledge and positive attitude of management towards HRD are needed for the success of any HRD initiatives. Hence, the data have been collected from the sampled respondents and shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Management's Knowledge and Positive attitude for HRD

Response	HRTC	HPTDC	Total
Yes	16(40.00)	22(55.00)	38(47.50)
No	13(32.50)	10(25.00)	23(28.75)
No opinion	11(27.50)	8(20.00)	19(23.75)
Total	40(100.00)	40(100.00)	80(100.00)
$\chi^2 = 1.812$; $\chi^2_{table} = 5.991$; $p > .05$			

Note: χ^2 denotes Chi-square, χ^2_{table} denotes Critical value or Tabular value of Chi-square.

ii) Figures in parenthesis represent percentage.

Source: Field survey.

The organization-wise data reveal that majority of respondents in both the organization (40.00 per cent in HRTC and 55.00 per cent in HPTDC) reported that management has the knowledge and positive attitude towards HRD. The calculated value (1.812) of χ^2 test is lower than the tabular value (5.991) indicating no significant difference in respondents' opinions. Therefore, it can be inferred that in a majority of cases management of both the organization has the knowledge and positive attitude towards HRD.

5.4. Management's Experience and Expertise

The opinion of the lower-level employees regarding management's experience and expertise in HRD has been analyzed in Table 4.

Table 4: Management's experience and expertise in HRD

Response	HRTC	HPTDC	Total
Yes	24(60.00)	26(65.00)	50(62.50)
No	10(25.00)	7(17.50)	17(21.25)
No opinion	6(15.00)	7(17.50)	13(16.25)
Total	40(100.00)	40(100.00)	80(100.00)
$\chi^2 = 0.686$; $\chi^2_{critical} = 5.991$; $p > .05$			

Note: χ^2 denotes Chi-square, $\chi^2_{critical}$ denotes Critical value or Tabular value of Chi-square.

ii) Figures in parenthesis represent percentage.

Source: Field survey.

About management's experience and expertise in HRD, the data in Table 4 reveal that out of total, 62.50 per cent opined that management of their organization has the experience and expertise in HRD. While 21.25 per cent didn't feel this. The organization-wise data reveal that the percentage of those who opined that management didn't have experience and expertise in HRD was found highest in HRTC. The application of χ^2 test shows that the calculated value (0.686) is lower than the tabular value (5.991) at a 5 per cent level of significance. It shows that there is no significant difference in respondents' opinions. Therefore, it can be inferred that the majority of respondents opined that management has the experience and expertise in HRD.

5.5. Use of Experience and Expertise

Now it is important to know whether management is using its skill, experience and expertise in formulating and implementing HRD programmes in the organization or not. The collected data have been given in Table 5.

Table 5: Opinion about the use of Experience and Expertise by the Management

Response	HRTC	HPTDC	Total
Yes	17(42.50)	16(40.00)	33(41.25)
No	13(32.50)	11(27.50)	24(30.00)
No opinion	10(25.00)	13(32.50)	23(28.75)
	40(100.00)	40(100.00)	80(100.00)
$\chi^2 = 0.588$; $\chi^2_{critical} = 5.991$; $p > .05$			

Note: χ^2 denotes Chi-square, $\chi^2_{critical}$ denotes Critical value or Tabular value of Chi-square.

ii) Figures in parenthesis represent percentage.

Source: Field survey.

Data about the use of experience and expertise by the management reveal that majority of respondents (42.50 per cent in HRTC and 40.00 per cent in HPTDC) believed that the management was using their experience and expertise. Whereas, 32.50 per cent in HRTC and 27.50 per cent in HPTDC believed that management was not using their experience and expertise. It is important to mention that out of the total respondents, 25.75 per cent didn't furnish their opinion on this question. The application of χ^2 test shows that the calculated value (0.588) is lower than the tabular value (5.991) which indicates that there is no significant difference in the respondent's opinion. Therefore, it can be inferred that less than fifty percent of respondents accepted the use of experience and expertise by the management.

5.6. Opinion about the Competence of Top management

The opinion of the sampled respondents about the competence of the top management has been shown in Table 6.

Table 6: Opinion about the Competence of Top Management

	Highly Incompetent	Incompetent	Neutral	Competent	Highly Competent	Total
S1. Competence of top management in motivating individual						
HRTC	3(7.50)	9(22.50)	7(17.50)	8(20.00)	13(32.50)	40(100.00)
HPTDC	25.00)	5(12.50)	5(12.50)	12(30.00)	16(40.00)	40(100.00)
Total	5(6.25)	14(17.50)	12(15.00)	20(25.00)	29(36.25)	80(100.00)
$\chi^2 = 2.787; \chi^2_{table} = 9.488; p > .05$						
S2. Competence of top management in understanding the problems						
HRTC	5(12.50)	11(27.50)	6(15.00)	6(15.00)	12(30.00)	40(100.00)
HPTDC	3(7.50)	9(22.50)	6(15.00)	12(30.00)	10(25.00)	40(100.00)
Total	8(10.00)	20(25.00)	12(15.00)	18(22.50)	22(27.50)	80(100.00)
$\chi^2 = 2.882; \chi^2_{table} = 9.488; p > .05$						
S3. Competence of top management in encouraging employees to participate in HRD programme						
HRTC	6(15.00)	9(22.50)	8(20.00)	6(15.00)	11(27.50)	40(100.00)
HPTDC	2(5.00)	7(17.50)	8(20.00)	9(22.50)	14(35.00)	40(100.00)
Total	8(10.00)	16(20.00)	16(20.00)	15(18.75)	25(31.25)	80(100.00)
$\chi^2 = 3.210; \chi^2_{table} = 9.488; p > .05$						

Note: χ^2 denotes Chi-square, χ^2_{table} denotes Critical value or Tabular value of Chi-square.

ii) Figures in parenthesis represent percentage.

Source: Field survey.

With regard to the competence of top management in motivating individuals, the data reveal that out of the total respondent, 32.50 per cent of respondents in HRTC and 40.00 per cent of respondents in HPTDC opined that top management is highly competent in motivating an individual in the organization. The calculated value (2.787) of χ^2 test is

lower than the tabular value (9.488) showing no significant difference in respondents' opinions. The mean value (3.675) is higher than the standard average mean score, that is, 3 on a 5-point scale. The deviation in respondents' opinion is noted at 1.300. It shows that the respondents' opinion is concentrated towards the higher side of the mean. Hence, it can be said that the majority of respondents believed that management is competent in motivating individuals.

Table 6 (a): Descriptive Statistics of the Opinion of sampled respondents about the Competence of Top Management

	Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation
S1	Competence of top management in motivating individual	3.675	1.300
S2	Competence of top management in understanding the problems	3.325	1.376
S3	Competence of top management in encouraging employees to participate in HRD programme	3.413	1.375

About the competency in understanding the problems, data depict about 45 per cent of respondents in HRTC and about 55 per cent of respondents in HPTDC opined that management is either highly competent or competent in understanding the problems faced by the employees of the organization. On the other hand, about 40 per cent in HRTC and about 30 per cent in HPTDC reported that management is not competent. The application of χ^2 test shows that the calculated value is lower than the tabular value. It reflects no significant difference in the opinion of respondents. The mean value (3.325) is higher than the standard average mean score and the deviation in the opinion of the respondents is noted at 1.376. It depicts that the opinion of respondents is concentrated towards the higher side of the mean score. Hence, it can be inferred that the majority of respondents believe

that top management was competent in understanding the problems faced by the employees in the organization.

Concerning the encouragement given by the management to its employees, the data reveal that majority of respondents (27.50 per cent in HRTC and 35.00 per cent in HPTDC) believed that management was highly competent in encouraging the employees to participate in the HRD programme. While 15.00 per cent in HRTC and 22.50 per cent in HPTDC believed that management was competent in this. Whereas, about 38 per cent of respondents in HRTC and about 23 per cent of respondents in HPTDC opined that management was either highly incompetent or incompetent in encouraging employees to participate in the HRD programme. The calculated value (3.210) of χ^2 test is less than the tabular value, which indicates no significant difference in the opinion of respondents. The mean value is higher than the standard average mean score, indicating no significant difference in the opinion of the respondents. Hence, it can be concluded that top management has the competence in encouraging employees to participate in HRD programme.

5.7. The willingness of Management toward the Provision of Training

At this point, it is important to analyze the opinion of the respondents about the willingness of management towards the provision of training to the employees of the organization. Therefore, the collected data have been shown in Table 7.

Table 7: Opinion about the willingness of Management toward the provision of training

Response	HRTC	HPTDC	Total
Yes	19(47.50)	25(62.50)	44(55.00)
No	13(32.50)	6(15.00)	19(23.75)
No opinion	8(20.00)	9(22.50)	17(21.25)
Total	40(100.00)	40(100.00)	80(100.00)
$\chi^2 = 3.456$; $\chi^2_{critical} = 5.991$; $p > .05$			

Note: χ^2 denotes Chi-square, $\chi^2_{critical}$ denotes Critical value or Tabular value of Chi-square.

ii) Figures in parenthesis represent percentage.

Source: Field survey.

The data reveal that out of total respondents, 55.00 per cent of respondents believed that management was willing to provide training to its employees. While 23.75 per cent of

respondents didn't believe this. The organization-wise data show that the respondents in HPTDC (62.50 per cent) has the highest number of those who believed that management was willing to provide training. The low calculated value of chi-square indicates that there is no significant difference in the opinion of the respondent. Hence, it can be said that in most of the cases management in both organizations was willing to provide training to its employees.

Conclusion

The management is the backbone of an organization. It not only organizes, direct and manage the affairs of the organization, but also encourage and motivate the human resources to enhance their capacity and capability to give their best to the organization. Until and unless management is willing to or have competency to formulate and implement the human resource development programme, the organization cannot initiate human resource development efforts. The study found that majority of employees in both the sampled corporations were of the opinion that the management of their respective corporation didn't incline towards the administrative philosophy of HRD. It was also found that majority of respondents accepted that management was willing to introduce the HRD programme in the organization. But the percentage of those respondents who didn't accept it or were restrained to say anything cannot be ignored. It gives an impression that the management of both organizations is not willing to introduce the HRD programme. However, the majority of respondents accepted that management of both the organization has the knowledge and positive attitude towards HRD. The study reveals that management has the experience and expertise in HRD and in most of the cases they use it in their respective corporation. Regarding competency of management the study shows that the management of both the organization is competent in motivating the individual, encouraging them to participate in HRD programme and willing to provide training to its employees.

References

- Bhatia, S. (2007, April). Human Resource Management: A Comparative Advantage. *The Indian Journal of Industrial Relations*, 42(4), 746-751.
- Billimoria, R. (1997, April-June). HRD Strategies for Globalization. *Productivity*, 38(1), 362-370.
- Jacob, K. (1973). *Personnel Management in India*. Udaipur: Himachal Pradesh.

- Jaiswal, A., & Singh, A. (2014, December). Role Of HRD Climate In Organizational Effectiveness In Indian Organization. *GJBM*, 8(2), 125-130.
- Karthik Trichur Sundaram (2020)
https://www.ijmra.us/project%20doc/2020/IJMIE_OCTOBER2020/IJMIE5Oct20-20077.pdf
- McLagan, P. A. (1989, January). Models for HRD Practice. *Training and Development Journal*, 41(9), 49-59.
- Patel, A. (2019, October). A Study on Employees Satisfaction Towards Performance Appraisal Practices. *International Journal of Research in Commerce & Management*, 10(10), 15-19.
- Rudrabasavaraj, M. (1987). *Dynamic Personnel Administration, Management of Human Resources*. Delhi: Himalaya Publishing House.
- Saini, D. S. (2005, April). HRD through Vocational Training: The Indian Model. *Indian Journal of Industrial Relations*, 40(1), 529-546. Retrieved from <https://www.jstor.org/stable/27767982>
- Scalia, S. (2016, February 16). *Human Resource Development: Definition & Importance*. Retrieved from <https://study.com/>: <https://study.com/academy/lesson/human-resource-development-definition-importance.html>
- Tiwari, R. K. (2001). Human Resource Development in Jharkhand. *Geographical Review of India*, 63(3), 368-371.
- Tripathi, S., & Hachiketa, T. (2002). *The Effect of Organizational Climate and Organizational Success*.